

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEBABI****FIRST NAME: ONEN FRANCIS****PROGRAM CODE: DARM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The term used to describe the usage of a source of information without giving credit to the original author:

Referencing

Source citing

Plagiarism¹

Academic writing

2. The term that describes a list containing all the items cited in academic writing

Citation

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, Fourth (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Bibliography**²
- Parenthesis
- Quotation
3. The following are the building blocks when constructing an argument except:
- Claim
- Question
- Evidence
- Discouraging the doubters from questioning the evidence**³
4. Which one of the following is not included among the aims of conclusion in academic writing?
- To leave readers with clarity of the claim
- To facilitate understanding of the significance of the claim
- To emphasize stating the claim in the later part of the conclusion**⁴
- To enhance mentioning the areas for future research
5. Which one of the following correctly describes a footnote?

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 38.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, 9th Edition (London: The University of Chicago Press, Ltd., 2018), 60.

⁴ Turabian, 111.

- Notes at the end of a page⁵**
- Notes at the end of a paragraph
- Notes at the end of a chapter
- Notes at the beginning of a sentence
6. The following are acceptable practices in academic writing except:
- Paraphrasing someone written work
- Quoting someone written work
- Copying with the proper citing of the citation sources
- Stating someone's work without giving credit to the original author⁶**
7. Which one of the following statements is the most correct statement?
- Conceptual framework and theoretical framework are noted as synonymous
- Inductive research uses a conceptual framework
- Deductive research uses a theoretical framework
- The conceptual framework facilitates grounding and understanding of the propagation of knowledge⁷**
8. All the following are important in dissertation writing except:
- Research title

⁵ Turabian, 148.

⁶ Turabian, 139 & 140.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019), 167.

- Plagiarism⁸**
 - Problem statement
 - Purpose statement
9. In discouraging discriminatory connotation, the following should be avoided except:
- Use of geographical connotations such as north, south, east, or west
 - Use of descriptions such as Western World
 - Use of salutations such as ‘Ms’ or ‘Mrs’ based on personal choice and preference⁹**
 - Respecting people association alongside convictions
10. The World Health Organization study guide recommends the following in the handling of numbers except:
- Non-breaking spaces instead of commas
 - Combining numerals and words
 - A time of day should be written in 12 hours¹⁰**
 - A date should be written as 11 May 2021 instead of 11/05/2021

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, Fourth (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁹ WHO, “*WHO Style Guide*,” Second Edition, (WHO, 2013), 56.

¹⁰ WHO, 28.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.